

The Modern Movement and Urban History

I will first of all thank all the organizers for assigning me the difficult task of opening the debate at this sixth conference of Docomomo. It is both an honor and an embarrassment for me to be asked to comment on "The Modern Movement and Urban History". An honor to throw some wood into the fire of scholarly discussion, and an embarrassment, because I am not, and this is something I should confess right now, a true believer in the "Modern Movement". Faithful to my master and friend Manfredo Tafuri, I can only put this term in quotation marks, for several reasons:

- first, because of the wide extension of radical design strategies throughout the XXth Century well beyond those of the founding "moderns". These strategies often took visual expressions that were traditionalist, but nonetheless incorporated attempts at breaking with eclecticism and historicism.
- second, because of the multiplicity of "movements" involved in modernism itself, and overlooked by the founding modern historians who developed narratives based on inclusion rather than exclusion. As soon as a thorough and objective record of the encounter between modernism and modernization is constructed, one is forced to detect parallel and contradictory movements.
- and third, because of the sheer propagandistic dimension the term "Modern Movement" has taken. After all, the slogan was not coined by Nikolaus Pevsner in his 1936 *Pioneers of the Modern Movement*, but exactly forty years before by Otto Wagner in *Moderne Architektur*.

A new stage in terms of research and preservation policies has to be acknowledged in many countries today, and the scarcity of publications has given place to an indigestible mass of monographs and studies, that no collective effort can sort out. This year's Docomomo conference is a meaningful step in a process of expansion, as it confronts scholarship from several continents.

Balancing these doubts that are by no means only my own, I am on the other side a true believer in Urban History. I will borrow here a definition given in 1994 by Swiss historian André Corboz in his introduction to F. Walter's *La Suisse urbaine 1750 1950*. Corboz identifies the *History of urbanism*, dealing with the "theories" and what I should call the methods of self-conscious transformation of urban space; the *History of cities*, dealing with their "morphological and typological evolution and their topographic peculiarities"; and *Urban History*, or the "history of the practices societies develop of their territory".

I will try to focus here on issues and situations dealing with these three levels, and mainly with the third and last one, as I guess from the program that urbanism and specific cities will be considered by many contributions to the conference.

Markers of ideals

Let me start by pointing to one of the long lasting tropes in the historiography of the "Modern Movement". Many narratives relative to the encounters between Modern architecture and the city have been constructed in the epic mode.

"Victorious" attempts at creating new towns, such as Costa's and Niemeyer's Brasilia or Le Corbusier's Chandigarh, are balanced by "failures", such as Le Corbusier's uncompleted Plan Voisin in Paris or Plan Obus in Algiers. Failure in these cases and many others has been often interpreted by architects themselves as the "betrayal" of political élites, unable to see the virtues of grand plans.

On the other hand, Modern architecture has been perceived by critics of a different persuasion as a cluster of strategies opposed not only to the existing city, but also to the very concept of city. Simplified interpretations of the History of urbanism are common and are often absorbed by contemporary architects. When Christian de Portzamparc affirms in 1995 (introduction to Olivier Mongin, *Vers la troisième ville ?*, Paris, Hachette, 1995) to be designing for the "Age 3" of the city, after "Age 1", i.e. the traditional continuous city, and "Age 2", i.e. the discontinuous city of Modernism, he overlooks, all the moments in which attempts at partial reforms have produced stimulating developments that have been consistently well-received.

In the case of Ernst May's *Frankfurt Siedlungen*, in relation to city expansion, or in relation to city reconstruction, as in Hans Scharoun's plan for the *Hansaviertel*, radical architecture has been able to produce workable contributions to the modernization of cities. This has been done less with global plans, like Scharoun's own 1946 *Kollektivplan* for Berlin, than with limited schemes providing convincing representations of a desirable future.

Here we meet of course the first pattern articulating Modern architecture and Urban History : *duration*. For me the issue is less to know what types of cities or of components of cities Modern architecture has generated directly or indirectly, than to question how Modern buildings condense and document past attitudes and uses. In short, how they belong both to intellectual history and the history of material culture in urban space.

If the chord of "failure" has so often been struck by historians, it is because failure is the index of a forbidden future. I will here inscribe my remarks within the theoretical framework provided by Reinhart Koselleck *Futures past : on the semantics of historical time*, originally published in 1979. The German historian locates historical present, that is the time of action, or of project in our particular case, at the intersection of the "space of experience" and the "horizon of expectation". French philosopher Paul Ricœur, in many writings such as *L'initiative* (1986), discusses the way the "horizon of expectations" seems to be fleeing on the "space of experience" shrinking in utopian discourse. This is, I believe, an excellent definition of many modernist strategies.

What the historical interpretation of Modern architecture can produce in this instance is to revive lost "horizon of expectations" or in other terms forgotten urban futures, that have become nonetheless sometimes part of contemporary urban practices. Former futures have not been systematically linked with Modernism however. In my investigation of Americanism, for instance, I have met many architectural aspects of the phenomenon that were not embodied by radical buildings –those of Walter Gropius, Le Corbusier, Mendelsohn or other Modernists, but by seemingly conservative designs.

But there are instances where Modern architecture has embodied the vision of the destiny of new nations, this is of course true of Brazil, as it is true, for instance, of inter-war Czechoslovakia. The Renaissance of the nation and the status of capital city regained by Prague had to be underlined by buildings breaking the former connections with Vienna and looking at radical strategies as developed in Paris or in Moscow.

In the case of Czechoslovakia or Finland, Modern architecture has almost taken the status of a

tradition condensing part of national identity. But Prague's architecture of the inter-war years, taken here as a brief example brings me to focus for a second again on the question of temporality. This short-lived production can be read according to a *synchronic* way as a component of European Modernism or of the emerging new Czech culture.

Fig. 1 – Ludvík Kysela, Bat'a commercial building on Venceslas Square, Prague, 1928-1929, photo Jean-Louis Cohen

If we want to frame an interpretation inscribed in Urban History, we have however to read it according to a *diachronic* thread, as a particular moment in the modernization of Prague, a process that had started with the Industrial revolution and immigration. Kysela's Bat'a building and Havlicek's and Honzik's Pension Institute bear witness of the two shaping forces in the process : advanced business strategies and progressive social policies.

I will not elaborate anymore, but we have here the most obvious figure in the articulation of the "Modern Movement" and urban History : architecture as a marker not of the internal changes of architectural discourse, but of the modernization process at large.

The core of this talk will however deal with other issues inscribed in temporality. I will try to use as illustrations analyses coming from my own research of the past years, namely projects dealing with French/German occupation, Paris's suburban belt, and with colonial Casablanca.

Markers of conflicts and unresolved issues

I would like to contrast with the idealized image of smooth modernization the dimension of conflict at the core of contemporary history at large, but also of Urban History. Urban space is shaped, determined by conflicts between nations, social classes and ethnic groups, and architecture is not immune, but rather exemplifies and condenses these conflicts.

There are of course rather benign conflicts. Rather basically, buildings remain markers of negotiations between different types of agents. They document the changes in zoning principles and building regulations (Baupolizei), and therefore give an account of the balance between public control and private interest. In this respect, episodes like the 1902 Paris urban regulation, drafted by Louis Bonnier, or the 1916 New York zoning ordinance, drafted by George B. Ford, are extremely interesting. Significantly, these regulations are shaped on new types of buildings, higher, more complex and more individualistic in both cases.

Common rule, as applied to the entire city, derives from radical architectural experiments –those of late Art Nouveau in Paris and of the massive early skyscrapers in New York. And this rule will then provide the framework for the practice of development for many decades, including the completion of buildings pushing the rule to its limit, like these two.

But there also more violent patterns of conflict, in which architecture is involved. I will focus here on the sequence of projects and buildings than can be observed in a territory extending from Switzerland to Belgium, and alongside which France and Germany have been constantly and rather brutally switching hegemony since the XVIIIth Century. And here we have an interesting manifestation of a diachronic pattern. In the sequence of Nazi (re)annexation of Alsace and Lorraine, from 1940 to 1944, and of French occupation of Baden, Rhineland and the Saar, from 1945 to 1955 in the latter case, Modern architecture condenses conflicts between states and long duration patterns of city development.

In contradiction with superficial views of architecture in Nazi Germany, the Germans sponsor modern traditionalists like Schmitthenner, as well as radical functionalists like Neufert, at that time head assistant to Albert Speer.

In the small village of Boust, the conflict is today documented by the remaining church of Steffann, a beautiful interpretation of Lorraine's rural heritage, as well as by the later and extremely different church of Pingusson, head planner in nearby Sarre.

Fig. 2 – Paul Schmitthenner, plan for the extension of Strasburg, 1942.

Fig. 3 – Georges-Henri Pingusson, plan for the reconstruction of Saarbrücken, 1946.

Not only do the French promote new radical plans, in this case for Sarrebruck, capital of Sarre, a region they planned to keep forever, but they also use the industrial context for experimentation such as Prouvé's prefabricated houses. But they also promote actively the ideals of Modernism, through exhibitions and publications.

In the case of Mayence, a medieval city located on the Rhine, Marcel Lods designs a reconstruction plan based on the Athens Charter, translated into German by the French and advertised by Gerald Hanning's extraordinary cartoons (Hanning had been the head designer for the Modulor in Le Corbusier's office).

But Lods' plans for a radical reconstruction of Mayence are blocked by public opinion and the French withdraw them, as Paul Schmitthenner, initially an authentic early Nazi, but indeed a great traditionalist designer, develops a more respectful plan for the central city and conservative-looking high-rises.

In short, whereas the Germans had been able to build several schemes without interference from local society, French projects were doomed as Allied occupation was meant to restore democracy, implying a public intervention fatal to radical plans (like in the case of Le Corbusier's Saint-Dié's plan). Buildings remaining today in Alsace, Lorraine, and Pingusson's former French Embassy in Sarrebruck still bear witness of these intense conflicts and belong to the region's urban history.

Fig. 4 – Henri Prost, plan for Casablanca, 1917.

I will now shift my focus south, to a scene of colonial conflict : the city of Casablanca, as practically refounded by the French during the Protectorate years –1912 to 1956. Here, too, plans and buildings have to be framed in a broad historical sequence. The city was of course shaped by strategies of domination that were alternatively or simultaneously brutal and subtle. But policies promoted by Gen. Lyautey and his followers also aimed at modernization not only of Morocco, but also of France, through the experience gained in a non-bureaucratic and technologically advanced society.

Fig. 5 – Auguste Perret, France-Maroc warehouse, Casablanca, 1915, photo Jean-Louis Cohen

The contradictions between these different sides of colonial Casablanca can be grasped at many levels. The first one is the issue of technological innovation. The colonial context and the freedom in respect to conservative controls helped Perret to develop in 1913 thin shell vaults featured in all major books of the 1920's, from Giedion to Hilberseimer.

More than thirty years later, the same context allowed the Honneger brothers, Swiss architects and contractors, to experiment with lightweight concrete systems, later to be used in their Geneva housing schemes.

The tall office or residential buildings are not only the index of urban regulation much more open to innovative high-rise projects than the Paris one, but also reveal the ambition of Casablanca's Jews to excel in architectural statements representing new typologies. These buildings also reflect the liberation from the *dhimma* or Islamic protection, forbidding Jews to build houses and synagogues that were higher than Muslim houses and mosques...

Architectural invention in Casablanca reveals the many facets of the leisurely colonial life, and also the modern face of a city born with the movies and the automobile, and whose most meaningful landmarks are not churches but cinemas and garages. Lyrical statements also appeared after 1945 in the work of the remarkable Jean-François Zevaco, who was obviously aware of the issues *L'Architecture d'aujourd'hui* devoted to Brasil.

But of course the determining conflict opposed the colonial bourgeoisie and a growing Moroccan working class, and here again, built programs are meaningful markers. Whereas the workers housing schemes of the 1920's were based on the imitation of ancient Moroccan or Andalusian quarters, post-1945 projects developed a more abstract geometry.

Fig. 6 – ATBAT Afrique (Georges Candilis, Shadrach Woods), "Beehive" housing block for Muslims, Casablanca, 1952.

This new geometry is nowhere more visible than in the "Beehive" low-cost building with stacked patios built by Georges Candilis and ATBAT-Afrique in 1952. It is in itself the expression of a contradictory strategy aiming at providing newly urbanized Muslims with

the collective housing they were aspiring to, without depriving them of their traditional patios.

A shift of references is visible here, from the early Moorish patterns found in Boyer's Townhall to the vertical villages surveyed later that helped Candilis to legitimize his high-rise designs.

In contrast to the simplistic views of the colonial city, often based on a naive projection overseas of Michel Foucault analyses, field research and interpretations reveal the complex and changing web of oppositions and conflicts inside Moroccan urban society. Architecture becomes as important as historical evidence as series of economic data or political archives. I will return to the reception of these buildings in today's Morocco.

Markers of sick, contested territories

But let me return to Paris with a third and last example, to focus on a cycle of projects spanning a period of 130 years, from the completion of a retardataire fortification belt in 1845 to its belated replacement by a triple ring of housing, parks and freeways in the 1970's.

Already obsolete at the time of its completion, the rampart was standing alone as an abandoned structure on which Parisians would go out for picnics. Shanties similar in many ways to Brazilian favelas would appear on the "zone" adjacent to the 33 km long ring, popularizing a term, used for instance by Guillaume Apollinaire in the title of one of his most famous poems. By 1930, 50.000 people would inhabit the zone in precarious conditions.

But what the chronicle of projects connected with the return of the belt to civilian life indicates is a sort of mutual attraction between innovative design and a territory considered by many to be in crisis. The first decade of discussion on the decommissioning of the rampart and the zone coincide with Eugène Hénard's investigation in modern town planning. His idea for the belt is to create a system of large parks and to unify the street network of Paris and the outlying suburb, instead of creating a new isolation belt of houses and parks.

Fig. 7 – Eugène Hénard, project for a "boulevard à redans" on the Paris fortifications, 1903.

In the first moments of the controversy, Hénard works specifically on an alternative to the fortification belt based on the invention of a new type of boulevard with indents, studied in two basic versions.

After the war, a new arrangement is finally put in place, whereby the rampart is scheduled to be replaced by housing and the "zone" by parks and sports facilities. This new organization will not be implemented as such, since the political pressure of the "zone" inhabitants will prevent their expropriation until Vichy's government authoritarian rule.

The ideal type of the community planned on the belt is the Cité universitaire, first designed by Bechmann. Of course, Le Corbusier's Pavillon suisse will completely break with the rules established by Bechmann. But Le Corbusier's encounters with the rampart and the zone are nonetheless a clear evidence of what I should call the opportunism of Modern architecture in dealing with urban issues. I will focus in this respect on two striking examples.

When Le Corbusier designs the 1922 Immeuble-villas, we now that the commission emanates from a program written by the "Groupe de l'habitation franco-américaine". But the letters of intent sent by the architect to the Groupe show that the lots selected for the scheme are all located on the Western segment of the former Fortifications, devoted to luxury housing. The exact dimensions of the blocks confirm the choice made by Le Corbusier at this early stage of using the most widely discussed urban enterprise of the interwar times to root his first provocative project in the field of collective housing.

An indication of his interest for the belt is given in the sketches that accompany *The City of Tomorrow*, published in 1925. He prescribes a presence of XXth century invention precisely on the perimeter of Paris, as an answer to previous major urban compositions.

In preparation for the 1937 International Exposition, Le Corbusier selects once again a site on the former rampart, at the Kellermann bastion, pretending to be at once producing a striking example of innovative housing architecture and preserving the old rampart. In short, we see here how a major modern architect uses a sensitive area of the city to stage his novel proposals.

To make a long story short, let's focus for a minute on the last episode of this Parisian saga. When the "zone" is finally cleared, in the 1950's, the State's civil engineers manage to use it to build a ring freeway and slab housing. The sketches of Raymond Lopez for the reconstruction of the areas give the impression of a thoroughly modern and empty Paris with the basic corner bistrot replaced by a cafeteria housed under a Niemeyer-esque shell... Altogether, built or unbuilt architecture remain eloquent witnesses of the former rampart's difficult destiny.

Markers of collective memory

To return to the notion of Urban History as a discussion of spatial practices, the question of memory has to be mentioned. I will not abuse the term of “places of memory”, that has proven so productive as a historical slogan, notably in the collective investigation led by Pierre Nora. There, the notion of “place” is essentially metaphorical. But, if I subscribe to the concept of collective memory, as defined by Maurice Halbwachs, there is no doubt that territories touched by modern urbanism keep their former meaning. This is the case with the Paris “zone”, still present in suburban memory, notably through songs and movies.

Fig. 8 – Marius Boyer, Banque commerciale du Maroc, Casablanca, 1930. photo Jean-Louis Cohen

To return now for a minute to Casablanca, the most striking buildings of the 1920's have become part of the urban landscape and their initial meaning has been lost. No one sees today in Boyer's bank an expression of colonial financial capital or in Brion's Bendahan's building the ambitious attempts of a Jewish community now reduced to a spectrum. Both buildings now bolster the pride Casablanca's residents take in a history of creativity opposed to the supposed lethargy of traditional cities.

At this point, we are forced to deal with politics and the place of political struggle in today's city. Architecture can also be a marker of past fights. Lurçat's school in Villejuif has remained since 1933 the evidence of a strategy aiming at providing the best services to a suburban proletarian township. On the contrary, Sert's and Torres-Clave's Casa Bloc in Barcelona has been transformed under Franco into a Guardia Civil barracks and has only recently been restored to its identity as an experimental building.

Both buildings remain vestiges of larger urban schemes for the development of suburbia in the case of Lurçat or for the complete reorganization of the Barcelona region –the Macià plan– with Casa Bloc. The theme of the conference is “the modern city facing the future”. I can only return now in conclusion to my initial skeptical remarks. With some happy exceptions like the Plan Piloto area of the large city that is

now Brasilia, there is no such thing as a fully “modern” city if we define it conventional terms. There are modern islands in the contemporary city that deserve our understanding and our care, and these two are good examples of fragment that are still pointing out to the project of modern architecture.

Concluding remarks

The buildings designed by modern architects have initially interiorized elements of urban cultures. They are now discrete, objective components of metropolises that have grown, and where their original subversive meaning is often obscured. The radical schemes and buildings of the Modern movement are not only in this regard markers of inventiveness, but also records of political, social and cultural change. They document the process of modernization as much as they crystallize new architectural ideals.

In terms of methodology, this condition implies a wide opening to parallel strategies. Art history cannot alone provide the conceptual framework for an interpretation of modern architecture as inscribed in urban history. A wide range of materials and issues have to be tackled, but salvation cannot be found only in better monographs. At this year's world historians' conference, the need for new synthesis has been discussed. Architectural history has yet to rediscover its desire for synthetic interpretation, in order to frame the necessary microstudies.

But, beyond the scientific criteria and objectives, what is at stake here is also the awareness broader audiences can build of the necessary conservation of modern buildings. Ginzburg's Narkomfin and Eileen Gray's Roquebrune house might be difficult to understand as major episodes in modern culture. I am convinced that, in order to address audiences beyond the professional and the academic ones, mediations have to be found, that would help citizens to see in Narkomfin a generous but doomed attempt at collectivizing daily life, and to perceive in E 1027 the search for a renewed life under the sun. These mediations can be found in narratives shaping Urban History as a powerful tool for the development of what Docomomo stands for.

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